

8T – Curvature Ripples and Entanglement

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present an additional way to analyze the process of entanglement. The first way as introduced in the 8T thesis revolves about spin. The following idea emphasis is the uniting arrows or links between the matter cluster, i.e. the observer and the measured object. To solidify the strength of the argument the primordial coupling constants, and in particular the duality of the Electron to the bosons of the weak interaction $[W^+, W^-, Z]$ will be presented.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The wave equation of the Bosonic class is represented by the wave equation, which is net curvature diverging on the metric tensor. that is by a five-vector.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} &\rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \\ \mu &= (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n) \\ \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V &= \nabla^2 N_V \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

Suppose we would like to execute an experiment in particle physics. The measured object can be either a Fermion such as the Electron or any Boson, which is net curvature diverging unbound. Since based on the second coupling term, the Electron is isomorphic to the Boson of the weak interaction as given by equation (1.61) in the Thesis, it is considered to possess the same effect during measurement. The following mathematical reasoning is needed. The measurer is arbitrary variation cluster that vanished into matter. The measurer is an infinite amount of matter.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i &= 0; \\ N &\rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

Assuming the measurer is a matter cluster of immense amount which stay as it is, it must have Bosons, which ensure it will retain its shape. Define the set of Bosons that are composing the arbitrary variation cluster, which is the observer, using functor:

$$\begin{aligned} \wp: Top &\rightarrow Set \\ T &= [N_{V_k} | K \in \mathbb{R}] \end{aligned} \quad (1.51)$$

The set (1.51) is representation of the type of Bosons that composes the observer. That is given by the mathematical relation:

$$\begin{aligned} T &\subseteq \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \\ A &= \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i; N \rightarrow \infty \right\} \\ T &\subset A \end{aligned}$$

Since the set T is the set of net curvature composing the observer, and the measured object is of the following class, i.e. net curvature diverging unbound, **even before** measurement or the experiment there exist a modification, those **ripples from the object and from the matter cluster interest with each other**. Just a observer itself is causing a major variation of manifold. Assuming again the measurer has inner curvature retaining its shape and preventing its decomposition. Therefore, the manifold has those infinitesimal quantities, either with spin one-half or spin one:

$$B = \left\{ \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}$$

With the existence of the measurer, the two sets are representing the system itself, no matter how far they are there exist now a collection of the two set under one new set. The measured object is B and the matter cluster is A .

$$A \cup B \rightarrow C$$

$$C = A + B$$

There exist a modification of the system due to the **mere existence of the observer**. The net curvature which are discrete ripples of curvature diverging are creating compositions with the net curvature diverging of the observer; they are now part on the single entity. In certain cases, the combinations of ripples creating new ripples of higher magnitude that are solutions of the primordial higher terms. The observer, which has Electrons in it, are getting modified from the wave-like nature of the measured particle, and vice versa. Moreover, once the sets are joint to a single entity, it is impossible to reverse the action of joining them. It is impossible to decompose which element were modified nor which ones came from the matter cluster and which belonged to the infinitesimal quantity. That idea of irreversibility can be represented by the existence of two or more possible decompositions with equal probabilities.

$$C \rightarrow A_1 + B_1 \in P(u_1)$$

$$C \rightarrow A_2 + B_2 \in P(u_2)$$

$$A_1 + B_1 \neq A_2 + B_2$$

$$P(u_1) = P(u_2)$$

The idea of observers as separated entity from the measured object is leading us far astray as we can possibly get according to the 8T author. Not only that, the observer and the measured object are united in one system, which can not be decomposed nor it is stops at larger distances. The mere existence of the measurer is effecting the system, modifying it to a new joint set of elements, which interact with each other. Since no two observers are identical, no two joints sets are identical; each observer is causing a different joint set to be created, or a unique entanglement. That root is different than the one taken in the thesis, which used spin variation to derive the effect of measurement on the system. The spin variation is encompassed with additional unit of energy quanta, which causes the system energy to vary, making the experiment impossible to make without changing the measured object spin and energy.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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